

DEVELOPMENT OF LEGAL COMPETENCES OF HEADS OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Today, in our republic, special attention is paid to the improvement of the content of preschool education and personnel training processes based on advanced foreign experiences and the development of legal competencies in leaders as an important direction of the educational process.

Improving the legal consciousness and legal competence of the leader in the pre-school educational organization is one of the most important conditions for ensuring the rule of law and strengthening legitimacy.

Along with the achieved achievements, it is possible to face some problems that prevent the formation of respect for human rights and freedoms, raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population, and increasing the level of legal literacy of citizens in the society:

- to improve the legal competence of the leader, first of all, work on legal education and training should be carried out systematically and organically. That is, the participation of the family, neighborhood and other institutions of civil society is necessary. The cooperation of the above organizations does not work equally without considering this issue as the work of law enforcement bodies or some state bodies;

- in the period of current globalization, scientific and technical development, innovative methods of raising the legal consciousness and legal competence of the leader, advanced means of propaganda, positive experiences of foreign countries in this regard are not effectively used;

- as a result of the lack of legal knowledge of the head of the organization, for example, causing cases of discrimination of the rights and legal interests of the head or employees of the organization by officials;

- lack of extensive use of legal information by the leader, lack of effective cooperation with civil society institutions and mass media in this field;

- the fact that the leader has not deeply assimilated the concepts of rights and duties, honesty and purity, as well as norms of etiquette, and is not familiar with some important aspects of the Constitution;

- to improve the legal consciousness and legal culture of the leader, to form an attitude of intolerance towards corruption and other violations;

- lack of balance between personal interests and the interests of society in raising the leader's legal consciousness and legal competence.

In order to improve the effectiveness of the work on increasing the legal consciousness and legal competence of the head of the organization, as well as to introduce modern methods of increasing legal knowledge in accordance with the ongoing socio-political changes, we

identified the following as the main tasks of increasing the legal competence of the head during our research:

- to establish a system of consistent delivery of the content and essence of social and economic reforms, adopted laws and state programs in our country. For this purpose, extensive organization of propaganda work, trainings, etc.
- to improve the legal competence of the leader, first of all, to achieve the systematic and organic conduct of education from the preschool education system;
- to organize legal and educational events on the formation of the legal competence of the head of the preschool educational organization, along with teaching the history, religion, and national values of our people, as well as to strengthen the sense of belonging to the country and patriotism by forming the feelings of pride in state symbols in every citizen;
- increasing the role of mass media in providing legal information, wide use of innovative methods of legal promotion, including expanding the use of web technologies. Organization of radio broadcasts, films, interviews with the participation of leaders within the framework of the topic;
- establishment of mutual cooperation between state power and management bodies, including law enforcement bodies and civil society institutions;
- an in-depth study of the scientific basis of increasing the legal competence of the leader in the society.
- preparation of question-and-answer manuals for the head and employees of the preschool educational organization on the legal issues they often face in their daily life and delivering them to the organizations;
- organization of legal consultation courses aimed at improving the legal knowledge of the head and employees of the preschool educational organization;
- organizing open classes, roundtable discussions, etc., aimed at improving the legal knowledge of the head and employees of the preschool educational organization.

The existing system of training of education personnel remains a system that ensures the preservation of a single educational space, which implements rapid and poorly predictable changes in society and the education system in the conditions of high instability of the external environment.

When training institutes and pedagogical institutes for improving the knowledge of leaders have their own departments, permanent and highly qualified teachers, it is possible to organize the educational process in a different way by creating variable programs and plans. In this case, it was necessary not only to better satisfy the requests of managers, but also to formulate these requests taking into account the initial level of readiness of managers for specific activities.

Thus, the training system is able to meet the expectations of the public in eliminating the crisis of legal competence of the manager and to help prepare the manager for legal activity in new conditions.

Researchers believe that the goal of the system of training leaders in the field of education is to establish a balance between the social requirements for their personality and activities and the insufficient readiness to perform their professional and official functions in the conditions of modern social changes.

Specific goals of training for leaders of educational institutions are not only focused on social order - in our case, these are the requirements of the characteristics of qualifications -

they also correspond to the needs of leaders as individuals. Formulated goals require new means, methods, and forms of organizing the educational process.

In terms of the studied problem, the leading tasks of professional development are as follows: improvement of legal skills, acquisition of additional legal knowledge; development of value indicators in legal activity, personal development.

As a result of training or retraining in the system of basic pedagogical education (secondary specialized or higher), pedagogical skills are continuous, professional qualities of a specialist exist and are preserved.

It is determined by the type of primary education received and confirmed by relevant documents.

A qualification defines a person's readiness for any type of work, but not always the actual ability to perform it. The previously unseen mobility, the variability of the content of professional activity requires the versatility of workers, the constant change of the character of the direction, the organization of the quality of work and continuous education. Opportunities for ultimate education systems that provide once- in-a- lifetime education now almost finished. This functional illiteracy caused the problem of technological unemployment of representatives of a number of professions .

According to Onushkin, competence is understood as a measure of mastery of a profession or specialty characterized by the level of readiness of its carrier to perform tasks of a certain level of complexity. This term means that the subject is ready to successfully solve problems and perform tasks related to a certain type of activity. In this sense, it is close to the term "competence".

Teacher qualification and competence are interrelated. Competence, as an indispensable professional and personal characteristic, is determined by the readiness and ability to perform professional and pedagogical functions in accordance with the norms and standards currently accepted in society. The unique characteristics of the leader, his skills and qualifications, combined with each other, allow to determine the dynamics of personal and professional development. The teacher training system is able to prepare the heads of educational institutions to work in new conditions, opens new perspectives for the development of the legal powers of the head of the educational institution. We find confirmation of this in the works of EMNikitin, VGP indak and others .

Leading forms of professional development:

Qualification courses are a form of training that provides training, retraining or improvement of skills in the field of specialized activity.

In the system of self-education and professional development, it plays the role of a link between discrete stages and organized educational stages.

Short-term seminars, meetings, etc. - a course aimed at studying the individual problems of education and upbringing, management of an educational institution.

Qualification forms of improvement are inextricably linked with functions of professional development. The term "function" is used in various senses: ability to act, role, property, authority, value, duty. Functions do not depend on specific tasks solved by the training system, its specific features. The training system performs the following functions:

compensatory - to fill educational opportunities that did not exist before or were missed;

adaptation - adapt to the new requirements of life in a dynamically changing society ;

gradually enriching a person's ability to act and his spiritual world ;
diagnostics - a set of procedures and methods for analyzing success in mastering educational material;

specialization - preparatory work for certain types of activity ;

predictive - predicting the nature and pace of social development.

According to the researchers, the effectiveness of training depends on the proportionality and consistency of educational programs in the system of professional development, the correct selection of priorities, rational sequence, interrelated courses, activation of independent work of students, preference for non-traditional forms of education.

The analysis of educational programs and textbooks in the legislation shows that the functions of this subject in the training system have not yet been clearly defined, and regular connections have not been established between the relevant courses (philosophy, economics). One on the one hand, there is the repetition of study materials in different courses , on the other hand, the excessive detail of some questions and the reduction of the nature of others.

In order to justify the choice of a certain educational technology in our study, let's dwell on the characteristics of adult education.

As the American teacher L. Shefknecht noted, "till now, there is no significant progress in the development of the theory of adult learning, because in several countries it is considered as a special subject of scientific knowledge." However, the technology of adult learning has a number of features. Let's dwell on their brief description:

- adult students, in addition to being known, seek to know how management practice has developed, what new effective systems, methods, tools have appeared and what legal sciences have been collected and recommended in this regard, they have the opportunity to apply their practical knowledge, skills and abilities in practice; It is no coincidence that in the late 1920s, the so-called forms and methods of activity-based teaching, based on the experience of adult students, appeared. Education should be practical, that is, it is necessary to find a teaching technology that solves this problem and ultimately enriches and diversifies practical knowledge.

A student rarely assumes the role of another student, because the adult position presupposes a mentoring stereotype, a category, which is so firmly occupied that many can no longer leave this role. Attempts to help teachers to abandon authoritarianism are likely to cause negative emotional reactions, making it difficult to establish fulfilling relationships both with each other and with the professionals of the professional development system;

The student has the leading role (so he is the student, not the student). Adults strive for self-awareness, independence, and self-governance. An adult student with a certain life experience believes in immediately applying the new skills, knowledge and qualities acquired. The educational process should be organized in the form of joint activity of the student and the teacher at all stages: planning, implementation, evaluation and to some extent correction;

adult educational activity is an independent or specially organized process that stimulates the need for self-affirmation and self-affirmation through the search for and successful overcoming of intellectual difficulties.

PISAmoylenko sees a methodological system of teaching, which includes the purpose, content, methods, tools and forms of teaching.

CIZmeev, looking at educational technology through the system of actions of the teacher and the student, defines this process as follows: "it is a system of scientifically based

actions of active students, the implementation of which leads to the achievement of a high-level educational process."

Teaching technology is understandable, but it is not the same as pedagogical technology, because it refers to the method of mastering the same educational material within a certain topic, topic, issue and selected technology. Instructional technologies are variable and have specific methods.

- They can be didactic in nature, - says TCNazarov. The task of teaching technology is to increase the teacher's efficiency by assigning creative functions to the teacher and to simplify it as much as possible.

Nevertheless, we consider the concept of "teaching technology" as a methodological system of teaching, including the form, methods and technical form of this process.

There are different teaching technologies; problem-based learning, conceptual learning, modular learning, developmental learning, differentiated learning, problem-based modular learning, etc. It is possible to develop legal competences among the leaders of educational institutions using different technologies of education, in our study we used technology of modular teaching and technology of concentration teaching.

In domestic and foreign studies (BL Bespalko, V. Goldshmidt, IIKulibaba, PFKpivosharova, VGPindak, etc.) devoted to the problem of modular teaching technology, there are different views on understanding. The module and its construction technology are developed both from the point of view of organizing the educational content and from the point of view of developing the form and methods of teaching.

The modular teaching technology proposed in our study is based on the system-activity approach to the educational process, according to which the module at the activity level forms the stages of access, knowledge and control as a part of the didactic cycle. In this, the educational activities of the teacher and students are linear, sequential and respectively indicative, executive and evaluative.

The modular organization of the educational process occurs where many educational components are united by their purpose and content, and the blocks differ from each other in terms of content, structure and purpose. After the learning objective is developed, the learning elements of the module are highlighted. For this, of the topic study material _ _ element-element analysis is used, according to which the content of the subject material is divided into elements.

The following teaching methods prevail in practical technology: genetic method, methods of didactic modeling of collective intellectual activity ("brainstorming", synectics, etc.), method of "pumping" information, method of leaning, errors, method of enlarged problems. Forms of training are suitable for them: educational experiment, game (didactic, business, simulation), immersion lecture, work on errors, group of forms of independent work (mutual teaching, self-study, educational consultation, etc.).

The modeling of the content of the project works in the institute of retraining of directors and specialists of the preschool educational organization and their professional development is based on a modular approach. In recent years, micro-modules have been added to educational programs (social, management, pedagogical-psychological) of preschool educational organization managers aimed at forming a common culture of pedagogical and management staff, increasing the opportunities for inter-module interaction and meeting

their needs. Social and pedagogical practices include economic, logical, ecological, management and legal practices.

The mechanism of implementation of concentrated learning is the use of teaching methods that take into account the dynamics of student performance. The high quality of concentrated training is achieved due to the consistency of all components of the educational process: purposeful, meaningful, procedural and control-evaluative.

The characteristic of the objective component is that it is not the objectives of individual lessons, but the objective of the learning unit, topic and unit. The characteristic of the procedural component in concentrated training is determined by the choice of one of the models of expansion of organizational units: study of one scientific subject for a certain period of time, expansion of one day or study week with study of one day, or two subjects. The implementation of the educational block is carried out through the main group forms of training organization, which do not change during the transition from block to block: introductory lesson, independent work, practical exercises and credit.

In our research, we follow PISA Moilenko's point of view. He distinguished the following components of educational technology: educational goal focused on results; content composition; organization of the educational process; teaching methods and tools; teacher's qualification level; methods of evaluation of educational results.

Let's take a look at each of the components.

First, there are the most general goals that express social and pedagogical ideals. The leader's activity has goals, because his desire is to be aware of the news of education. Process goals should be consistent with outcomes.

Secondly, the content of the information provided for learning and mastering is a set of tasks and exercises that must be performed in order to master skills and acquire experience in legal activity. The contents of the lessons in the collected form are presented in the curriculum, in the extended form - in the training manual, training manuals.

The content should be structured (in terms of problem blocks, competency modules, credits, etc.) to help achieve certain knowledge, skills, abilities and qualities in a step-by-step and visual manner.

VGPindak distinguishes the following principles for choosing the content and structure of educational material:

1. The principle of priority is the significance of the learned knowledge in solving the most important tasks in the field of educational institution and educational process management.

2. Identify a number of methodological and practical ideas that reflect the current level of science and practice.

3. The principle of openness, which allows the inclusion of additional information from various fields of science in order to strengthen the leading ideas of the courses.

4. The principle of IT flexibility modularity, which allows the author to add additional elements to the composition and create compositional units.

differentiation, which implies the possibility of acquiring the same material at different levels: basic, "developed", deep.

6. The principle of cooperation, which includes the selection of content aimed at solving specific pedagogical problems.

At the same time, the nature of interaction between students and teachers in solving problems serves as a basis for the development of legal thinking in students.

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